

HIGH-MODULUS, HIGH-PERFORMANCE CARBON FIBER FROM PITCH PRECURSOR

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Union Carbide "Thornel"^[1] Type P carbon fibers are made from commercial coal tar or petroleum pitch, which is converted to anisotropic mesophase or liquid crystal state for spinning. The as spun fiber is highly oriented such that the essentially flat aromatic polymer molecules are parallel to the fiber axis. This orientation is maintained through subsequent thermal processing to the carbonized state, and results in a fiber capable of achieving high modulus and high tensile strength.

Mesophase pitch based fibers are currently being produced commercially in several forms: continuous 1,000 and 2,000 filament strand with Young's Modulus of 380-520 GPa and 2.1 GPa tensile strength used in structural applications; a carbon fiber fabric with Young's Modulus from 140-310 GPa used in carbon/carbon composites, ablative applications and structural applications; a low modulus (170 GPa) mat product used in sheet molding compounds to impart electrical conductivity; and a milled mat used in injection molding compounds to improve electrical conductivity, resistance to heat distortion, and improve wear characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

Union Carbide Corporation has developed a process for making high modulus carbon fiber from low cost commercial pitches. The process is based on the novel concept that the liquid crystalline phase (mesophase) produced from aromatic pitches can be oriented by the shear forces which occur during spinning and drawing into filaments. The as spun fibers are still thermoplastic. To render the fiber infusible, an oxidative cross linking step is required to thermoset them. Any number of oxidants are suitable but air has proven to be the least costly. The oxidation step is similar to that commonly employed with PAN based carbon fibers but from a process standpoint is quite different since there is no need for tensioning to maintain preferred orientation. After the yarn has been thermoset it can be carbonized at high heating rates.

CONTINUOUS STRAND PRODUCTS

The outstanding characteristic of mesophase pitch based carbon fibers as compared to PAN based carbon fibers is that high Young's Moduli are much more easily obtained. When introduced in 1976, Union Carbide's standard "Thornel" P55 had a modulus of 380 GPa (55×10^6 psi) and 1.21 GPa (175,000 psi) tensile strength. Although many stiffness critical applications could accommodate fibers of low tensile strength, these high modulus, low strength fibers could not be handled economically in manufacturing processes. Union Carbide studies had indicated that intrinsic strength of the mesophase pitch base fibers is over 3.45 GPa (500,000 psi) as determined by short gauge measurements on single filaments. Studies also indicated that the factors responsible for lower effective strength are: fused filaments, voids and inorganic inclusions, acting as stress concentration points. Work is in progress to eliminate these factors and current production "Thornel" P55 averages about 2.07 GPa (300,000 psi). The improvement of tensile strength with time is indicated in Table 1.

TABLE 1
TENSILE STRENGTH OF PITCH BASE CARBON FIBERS
CONTINUOUS FILAMENT "THORNEL" P55

This leads us to believe that the average tensile strength of production in the fiber will be 2.75 GPa (400,000 psi) range in the near future. With the advent of fibers with tensile strengths in the 2.07 GPa (300,000 psi) range the handleability problem has been greatly reduced and application development is proceeding rapidly. A number of the applications under consideration are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2
APPLICATIONS FOR HIGH MODULUS PITCH BASED CARBON FIBERS
GRADES VSB-32 (P55) AND VSB-32S (P55S)

Carbon/Carbon Composites
 Automotive Drive Shafts
 Helicopter Fuel Pods
 Marine and Recreational Boating Structural Applications
 Metal Matrix Composites
 Industrial Tools
 Sweep and Skull Oars
 Rocket Launcher Tubes and Hubs
 Ramps and Lifts for Aids to Handicap
 Hospital and Diagnostic Equipment
 Automotive Modulus Critical Panels and Supports

Continued processing innovation and quality improvements have permitted the introduction of several products in the ultra-high modulus range.

TABLE 3
PROPERTY COMPARISON OF PITCH FIBERS

<u>Grade</u>			<u>VSB-32</u> <u>P55</u>	<u>VSC-32</u> <u>P75</u>	<u>VS-0054</u> <u>P100</u>
Density		mg/m ³	2.02	2.06	2.10
Tensile Strength (10" gauge length)		GPa (10 ³ psi)	2.07 (300)	2.07 (300)	2.07 (300)
Tensile Modulus		GPa (10 ⁶ psi)	380 (55)	517 (75)	688 (100)
Coef. of Thermal Expansion	1/10 ^F	Longitudinal	-.5 x 10 ⁻⁶	-.7 x 10 ⁻⁶	
		Transverse	15 x 10 ⁻⁶	15 x 10 ⁻⁶	

"Thornel" P75 carbon fibers with a modulus of 517 GPa (75 x 10⁶ psi) were introduced commercially several months ago. Prepregging, filament winding and other commercial processes have demonstrated handleability and suitability of this product for advanced composites. Technical programs are in progress to commercialize 690 GPa (100 x 10⁶ psi) modulus carbon fibers. Limited quantities of 690 GPa (100 x 10⁶ psi) modulus fibers have been made available for various research and development programs. Our studies have demonstrated a high probability of producing pitch base carbon fibers with Young's Modulus of 827 (120 x 10⁶ psi), technology programs have been initiated to demonstrate that fibers of this high modulus can be produced. Although the primary use of the ultra-high modulus products of today is in the aerospace/aircraft application field, future modulus critical applications may be identified in the industrial/automotive areas. Table 4 gives a few examples of these applications.

TABLE 4
APPLICATIONS FOR ULTRA-HIGH MODULUS PITCH BASED CARBON FIBERS
GRADES VSC-32 (P75), VSC-32S (P75S) AND VS-0054 (P100)

Metal Matrix Composites
 Space Antennas, Arrays and Structures
 Outerspace Telescopes
 Carbon/Carbon Composites
 Push Rods For High Performance Autos

The wide range of modulus available with pitch base fiber will permit the production of products with modulus tailored to the application if the volume and economics justify.

The very low shear strength realized in composites has also been a major factor which has delayed the development of commercial applications for pitch base carbon fiber. Recent advances in treating capability have led to marked increased of shear strength of the high and ultra-high modulus carbon fiber in plastic matrix composites.

TABLE 5
COMPARISON OF SURFACE TREATED PITCH BASE CARBON FIBERS

<u>Grade</u>	<u>VSB-32</u> <u>P55</u>	<u>VSB-32S</u> <u>P55S</u>	<u>VSC-32</u> <u>P75</u>	<u>VSC-32S</u> <u>P75S</u>
Tensile Strength GPa (10" gauge length) (10^3 psi)	2.07 (300)	2.07 (300)	2.07 (300)	2.07 (300)
Tensile Modulus GPa (10^6 psi)	379 (55)	379 (55)	517 (75)	517 (75)
Torsional Shear Strength GPa (10^3 psi)	0.034 (5)	0.055-0.069 (8-10)	0.028 (4)	0.041-0.055 (6-8)

Because of the strong demand and potential applications, treatment processes were developed initially for the "Thornel" P75 product. "Thornel" P75S is commercially available with a surface treatment that yields a shear strength of 0.041-0.055 GPa (6,000-8,000 psi) in epoxy matrix composites. Surface treatments have also been developed for the 379 GPa (55×10^6 psi) modulus product. Only limited quantities of "Thornel" P55S have been available in the marketplace. Experimental "Thornel" P100 carbon fibers are not available in a shear treated fiber, since the primary applications envisioned are in metal matrix composites. However, a treated fiber in this grade could be available if the demand justified the development of such a product.

Strand and limited composites data on several of the relatively new pitch base carbon fibers are listed in Table 6 and are compared with "Thornel" 300 and "Thornel" 50 (PAN).

TABLE 6
 TYPICAL PROPERTIES OF "THORNEl" HIGH-MODULUS
 CARBON FIBERS AND THEIR COMPOSITES

	Units	"Thorne1" 300	"Thorne1" 50 (PAN)	"Thorne1" P55 (Pitch)	"Thorne1" P75S (Pitch)
Tensile Strength (10" gauge length)	GPa (10 ³ psi)	3.10 (450)	2.41 (350)	2.07 (300)	2.07 (300)
Tensile Modulus	GPa (10 ⁶ psi)	231 (33.5)	379 (55)	379 (55)	517 (75)
Density	Mg/m ³	1.75	1.81	2.02	2.06
Filaments/Ply		1000/3000/6000	3000/6000	1000/2000	2000
<u>UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES*</u>					
Tensile Strength (Coupon)	GPa (10 ³ psi)	1.55 (225)	1.21 (175)	1.03 (150)	0.79 (115)
Tensile Modulus	GPa (10 ⁶ psi)	138 (20)	228 (33)	234 (34)	303 (44)
Flexural Strength	GPa (10 ³ psi)	1.79 (260)	1.31 (190)	0.83 (120)	0.69 (100)
Flexural Modulus	GPa (10 ⁶ psi)	131 (19)	200 (29)	193 (28)	262 (38)
Compressive Strength	GPa (10 ³ psi)	1.59 (230)	0.83 (120)	0.48 (70)	0.41 (60)
Compressive Modulus	GPa (10 ⁶ psi)	138 (20)	206 (30)	193 (28)	241 (35)
Short Beam Shear	GPa (10 ³ psi)	0.12 (17)	0.069 (10)	0.034 (5)	0.062 (9)
Coef. of Thermal Exp. Longitudinal	1/10C	-.16x10 ⁻⁶ 8.3x10 ⁻⁶	-.22x10 ⁻⁶ 8.3x10 ⁻⁶	-.28x10 ⁻⁶ 8.3x10 ⁻⁶	-.38x10 ⁻⁶ 8.3x10 ⁻⁶
Transverse					

* 60 v/o fiber in high performance epoxy resins

These properties are typical for various epoxy resin systems, but should not be used as design values. The composite property of most interest is tensile modulus which has excellent translation in all fibers. Tensile, flexural and compressive strength of the pitch based fiber composites are lower than expected for the fiber properties. Studies are underway to better understand and hopefully improve these composite properties. "Thorne1" P55 carbon fibers are currently available as a 1,000 and 2,000 filament product. A 4,000 filament product is being developed with a target availability in 1980 followed by a future 8,000 filament product.

FABRIC PRODUCTS

Since pitch base fibers develop high modulus with ease and without necessity of tensioning, fabrics can be woven from thermoset strands and then converted to the high modulus carbon product. The product properties for the high modulus fabric grades, VCB-20, VCB-45, VCC-20 and VCC-45 and their composites are highlighted in Table 7.

TABLE 7
PITCH FABRIC GRADES

<u>FABRIC PROPERTIES</u>				
<u>Grade</u>	<u>VCB-20</u>	<u>VCB-45</u>	<u>VCC-20</u>	<u>VCC-45</u>
Weave(Harness Satin)	8	8	5	5
Weight, g/m ²	510	510	280	280
Filament Count/Yarn Bundle	2000	2000	1000	1000
Fiber Strength (Strand) GPa	1.38	1.38	1.55	1.55
(10 ³ psi)	(200)	(200)	(225)	(225)
Fiber Modulus (Strand) GPa	138	310	138	310
(10 ⁶ psi)	(20)	(45)	(20)	(45)
<u>COMPOSITE PROPERTIES</u>				
Tensile Strength GPa	0.269	0.303	0.345	0.331
(10 ³ psi)	(39)	(44)	(50)	(48)
Tensile Modulus GPa	38.6	88.3	39.3	96.5
(10 ⁶ psi)	(5.6)	(12.8)	(5.7)	(14.0)
Flexural Strength GPa	0.372	0.372	0.393	0.379
(10 ³ psi)	(54)	(54)	(57)	(55)
Flexural Modulus GPa	37.9	84.1	37.9	89.6
(10 ⁶ psi)	(5.5)	(12.2)	(5.5)	(13)
Compressive Strength GPa	0.331	0.207	0.345	0.207
(10 ³ psi)	(48)	(30)	(50)	(30)
Short Beam Shear Strength GPa	0.030	0.023	0.032	0.022
(10 ³ psi)	(4.4)	(3.4)	(4.6)	(3.2)

Grade VCB is produced from a 2,000 filament strand woven into an 8 HS weave that is processed into a 138 GPa (20 x 10⁶ psi) or 310 GPa (45 x 10⁶ psi) modulus product. Grade VCC is produced from a 1,000 filament strand woven into a 5 HS weave that is processed to a 138 GPa or 310 GPa (20 or 45 x 10⁶ psi) modulus product. Both products are available at a 106 centimeter (42 inch) nominal width fabric. Other widths can be made available on a to order basis.

Fabrics currently provide the biggest volume applications of pitch base carbon fibers. These applications consist primarily of marine components, carbon/carbon aircraft brakes and parts for solid propellant rocket nozzles. We also believe that pitch base fabrics can find use in complex shapes used in automotive and industrial applications that require critical positioning of the reinforcement such as roof sections and door panels.

MAT PRODUCTS

Mat products, introduced in 1973, were the first commercial high modulus pitch base carbon fibers available from Union Carbide. Grade VMA mat is produced from blow spun pitch, it consists of fibers varying in length from 2.54-7.62 centimeters and approx. 0.009 mm in diameter, it is held together by their mechanical interlocking. Properties of Grade VMA pitch base mat are shown in Table 8.

TABLE 8
PITCH BASE MAT PRODUCTS GRADE VMA
FILAMENT PROPERTIES

Density, Mg/m ³		2.0
Tensile Strength	GPa	1.38
	(10 ³ psi)	(200)
Tensile Modulus	GPa	172
	(10 ⁶ psi)	(25)
Diameter, mm		0.009

MAT PROPERTIES

Bulk Density	kg/m ³	36.0
	(lb/ft ³)	(2.25)
Areal Density	g/m ²	352
	(lb/ft ²)	(0.07)
Electrical Resistivity,	10 ⁻⁴ ohm-cm	7000
Thermal Conductivity,	W/m°C	.035
	Btu in/n/Ft ² °F	(0.24)

Typically single filament properties are 172 GPa (25 x 10⁶ psi) Young's Modulus and 1.38 GPa tensile strength. Although considerable interest has been demonstrated in Grade VMA, the granulated, milled and reconstituted forms have become the most popular varieties. Grade VMC is a chopped variety comprised of approx. 1.27 centimeter cubes. Grade VMD is the granulated form consisting of fibers measuring approx. 1 mm in length. The milled form is Grade VME and it consists of fibers measuring approx. 100 mm in length. Grade VMF is the reconstituted veil mat form that weighs less than 100 gms/m².

The applications for mat products are quite diversified including friction modification and conductive applications. Friction applications, which use primarily Grade VMD and VME in compositions to improve performance and replace asbestos, include automotive brake applications and clutch plate facings. The electrically conductive composite obtained through the use of veil mat has received increased attention for radio frequency interference (RFI) shielding applications.

AVAILABILITY PITCH BASED PRODUCTS

The present high demand for pitch base carbon fibers has resulted in the limited availability of product to expand current applications and explore new applications. Union Carbide's current production capacity is limited to approx. 22-34,000 kg/year of carbon fiber according to product description. Facility expansions are currently in progress that should resolve the short supply by mid 1980.

TABLE 9
PITCH BASE CARBON FIBER CAPACITY
CONTINUOUS FILAMENT

Current	22-34,000 kg/year
Mid 1980	77,000 kg/year
Jan - 1981	114,000 kg/year
Mid 1981	228,000 kg/year

MAT PRODUCTS

Current	91,000 kg/year
Mid 1980	136,000 kg/year

Projected capacity will be 77,000 kg/year by the first quarter of 1981. Other expansion programs are in process that will bring total capacity to 228,000 kg/year by the middle of 1981. Engineering and process development programs are in progress that ensure that a facility can be available for very high volume production within 24-30 months should the market warrant.

PAN BASE CARBON FIBERS

Although it is the intent of this paper to deal primarily with carbon fibers manufactured from pitch precursor it would be misleading if a brief summary of Union Carbide's efforts in regarding to PAN base carbon fibers was not included. In 1970 Union Carbide Corporation entered into a technology exchange agreement with Toray Industries of Japan. The combined efforts of both companies have led to the development of totally integrated plant for the production of the polyacrylonitrile precursor and a wide variety of carbonized products. In April 1980 ground was broken at Greenville, SC and construction was initiated on this totally integrated plant. The new plant will be operational in mid 1981 and will have an initial annual capacity of approx. 450,000 kg/year (1 million lbs). Our long term plans for this facility permit expansion to insure that production facilities meet the growing demand for "Thornel" 300 carbon fibers at economical prices. The new facility will have the capacity of producing a full line of moduli and filament count products but will be intended primarily for "Thornel" 300 for the aircraft and aerospace industries.

PAN based "Thornel" 300 and "Thornel" 50 carbon fibers feature a high degree of uniformity and a high level of demonstrated performance in a variety of aerospace/aircraft, industrial and sporting goods applications. These fibers are commercially available in several filament counts from 1,000 (1K) to 6,000 (6K). A new product consisting of 15,000 filaments (15K) was introduced in early 1980. It is particularly well suited for automotive and pultrusion applications. It has demonstrated performance comparable to 3K and 6K fibers at several customer locations. A 30,000 filament (30K) filament product was also introduced in early 1980. It is being considered in pultrusion, tooling and other applications.

REFERENCES

- 1 "Thornel" is a registered trademark of Union Carbide Corporation.